

Numerical assessment of the influence of a R744 cooling unit design and components on the overall carbon footprint of a light refrigerated vehicle

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ABSTRACT

To meet the upcoming challenge of environmental sustainability, refrigerated transport is required to address energy efficiency and use sustainable fluids, namely natural refrigerants, at the same time taking into consideration the typical constraints of mobile systems, i.e. space and weight, system complexity, reliability and ease of servicing and maintenance.

In this study, the design of a R744 refrigeration system employed on a light commercial vehicle used for urban delivery of fresh products (4-5 kW at 0°C) is considered. The effects of different system architectures, controls and components are numerically evaluated focusing on the trade-off between the increase of the unit complexity, leading to higher energy efficiency of the sole cooling system, and the decrease of the unit overall encumbrance and weight, leading to lower carbon footprint of the vehicle.

Numerical results show that the use of an ejector can enhance the unit COP up to +28.6% for high ambient temperature conditions (40°C). A compact unit design based on the use of a light and efficient variable-speed scroll compressor leads to a reduction in carbon emissions of an average delivery mission between -17.9% and -34.4%, depending on climatic conditions. The effects of evaporator sizing on the system performance and emissions are discussed. The overall carbon footprint of the units over their entire life cycle is assessed, highlighting that more than 95% of the equivalent CO₂ emissions are related to system operation. The use of natural refrigerant R744 reduces the direct leakage emissions to negligible values.

Keywords: Refrigerated Transport; Carbon Dioxide; Energy Efficiency; Weight; Design Optimization; Carbon footprint

1. INTRODUCTION

Refrigeration plays a crucial role in ensuring quality and safety of perishable products, such as food or pharmaceuticals. Over 1.12 billion people in the world face immediate risks related to lacking refrigeration, causing significant food loss and preventing a proper fight to hunger and malnutrition (Baha et al., 2025). In 2024, approximately 5.4 billion pieces of refrigeration equipment were estimated to be in operation worldwide and the market is expected to grow especially in underdeveloped areas, with a sevenfold increase of size in Africa and fourfold increase in South Asia by 2050 (Baha et al., 2025). On the other hand, the substantial growth of the refrigeration sector worldwide will determine an increase in carbon emissions linked to the operation of refrigeration systems. According to UNEP and FAO (2022), the current cold chain already contributes up to 4% of the global emissions, highlighting the crucial importance and need of developing new sustainable refrigeration solutions with limited impact on the environment.

Within the cold chain, refrigerated transport represents an important yet impactful step: it has been estimated that it accounts for nearly 25% of the total cold chain emissions (IIR, 2021). This sector has seen significant growth in recent years, reaching a total of approximately 5.7 million refrigerated road vehicles worldwide (Baha et al., 2025), and with further increase foreseen for the next decades. Demanding operating conditions like vehicle speed, vibrations and accelerations (Tassou et al., 2009), together with highly variable thermal load, are essential boundaries to be considered for system design,

which often results in oversized units (Maiorino et al., 2021) and consequent non optimized partial load operation.

Moreover, refrigerant leakages represent a major issue in transport applications, with reported leakage rates which can be as high as 165% of the Transport Refrigeration Unit (TRU) initial charge over the system lifetime (United Nations, 2017). Current market is almost entirely based on synthetic refrigerants (HFCs and HFOs): while R404A and R134a have been the most commonly used fluids in the last years, the phase down, enforced by the F-gas regulation in EU and the Kigali amendment worldwide, led to the identification of retrofitting fluids, like R452A, R449A and R442A (Minetto et al., 2023), still characterized by a significant Global Warming Potential (GWP). Overall, there is therefore a critical need for a comprehensive evaluation of the total carbon footprint of road refrigerated transport units to reduce emissions associated with both the unit operation and the refrigerant leakages.

Vapour compression systems still represent the vast majority of road TRU market, as documented by Fertel et al. (2023), who reported that 95.3% of refrigerated vehicles in France in 2022 still relied on vapour compression systems. Given the dominant share of the market covered with this technology, research studies need to be focused on the development of more efficient vapour compression units which, at the same time, should be designed to operate with natural refrigerants, to reduce their overall carbon footprint. An in-depth review on the use of natural working fluids in transport refrigeration by Minetto et al. (2023) highlighted that, while industrial manufacturers have already developed and put in the market natural refrigerants-based solutions for specific sub-sectors such as marine transport (Ladam, 2021; Söylemez et al., 2022) or intermodal containers refrigeration (Carrier, 2017), only a few solutions can be found regarding road transport refrigeration.

Hydrocarbon-based TRUs have been investigated both by research studies (Colbourne et al., 2017) and industrial manufacturers (Natural Refrigerants, 2022; Cooling Post, 2022), thanks to the simple refrigeration cycle structure and efficiency allowed by the hydrocarbons thermodynamic properties. However, almost all the mentioned systems employed hydrocarbons in a primary circuit kept outside of the refrigerated body and employed a secondary fluid to deliver the cooling effect inside the refrigerated compartment, to avoid potential flammability issues inside the confined space of the insulated box.

On the other hand, CO₂ (R744) is a non-toxic and non-flammable fluid, but its thermophysical properties require specific and more complex system design to achieve a high efficiency. A few prototypes have been proposed by industrial manufacturers (Carrier, 2016; Cooling Post, 2020), although being developed for mobile trailers which can be transported on the road. A few interesting examples of employment of R744 for refrigerated trucks have been reported in the last couple decades by another industrial manufacturer (Micheletto and Rosso, 2004: R744 system with eutectic plates for frozen food transportation; Cold Car, 2015: R744 system with photovoltaic panels for fresh food transportation) demonstrating good potential; however, such prototypes have never been further developed and launched on the market.

To the best knowledge of the Authors, no R744 TRU for light commercial vehicles is currently available on the market. Numerical research activities carried out before the present study (Artuso et al., 2020; Fabris et al., 2021; Fabris et al., 2024a) assessed that a R744 transport refrigeration system developed for a light commercial vehicle can achieve COP values higher than commercially available HFC systems even at high ambient temperature, but at the same time highlighted that the increased weight of the refrigerated unit due to its schematic complexity and components bulkiness can lead to slightly higher fuel-related emissions.

Consequently, significant reductions in the carbon footprint can be done through proper materials choice and component design. The influence of components choice, insulating materials and refrigerant on the cost and energy performance of TRUs has been recently investigated by Ramirez-Quintero et al. (2025), although an already phased-out HCFC refrigerant was considered in that study. The implementation of photovoltaic panels on the roof of the refrigerated vehicle was also investigated (Rossetti et al., 2022; Maiorino et al., 2024), showing great potential to enhance the energy balance of

refrigerated trucks.

This study focuses on the optimal design of a R744 TRU for light commercial vehicles and numerically evaluates different R744 unit configurations, to identify the best trade-off between COP and unit weight, with the overall goal of minimizing the global carbon footprint. To find the optimized conditions, numerical simulations are performed for different layouts, entailing different complexity level in the circuit arrangement, evaporator size and control logic. In addition, the influence of different climatic conditions is also accounted for in the evaluation of the overall carbon footprint of the proposed solutions.

2. COOLING UNIT LAYOUTS

The objective of this study is the design and performance evaluation of a transport refrigeration unit based on the use of natural working fluid R744 and designed to fulfil the cooling needs of a light commercial vehicle, employed for last mile delivery of chilled goods in urban environment. The design cooling power is equal to 4-5 kW of Medium-Temperature (MT) cooling capacity, at a set point internal air temperature equal to 0°C. The internal temperature of 0°C has been chosen in accordance to the value prescribed in the procedure for determining the efficiency of class A mechanically refrigerated equipment, as defined in the ATP agreement (United Nations, 2024).

In this study, two different TRU layouts are proposed. Each of these layouts then presents the possibility to operate in different configurations, modifying the refrigerant circuit to include or exclude certain components.

2.1 Modulated orifice unit

Firstly, a modulated orifice (MO) unit, based on the results of previous research studies (Artuso et al, 2020; Fabris et al., 2021; Fabris et al., 2024a), is considered, and its simplified layout is presented in Figure 1. It is a traditional back-pressure concept, with a fixed-speed semi-hermetic compressor (operating at the rated velocity of 1450 rev min⁻¹) and a modulating high-pressure valve (HPV).

Figure 1: Modulated orifice (MO) unit layout.

Different configurations are available by including or excluding the ejector and the auxiliary evaporator acting on the opening of solenoid valves, as presented in Figure 2, where red colour is used to represent high-pressure level, green represents low-pressure level and light green, when present, represents an intermediate pressure level. Dashed lines are used to indicate the portions of the unit not used in the

considered configuration.

The back-pressure (BP) configuration occurs when excluding both the ejector and the auxiliary evaporator, as displayed in Figure 2a. Figure 2b presents the schematic of the ejector (EJ) configuration, where a two-phase ejector is added in parallel with the HPV, for exploiting part of the available expansion work at the outlet of the gas cooler to provide a pressure lift to the refrigerant from evaporation to liquid receiver pressure level, thus increasing the compressor suction pressure and consequently reducing the compressor power consumption required to provide a fixed cooling effect. The compressor size is chosen to always choke the ejector motive nozzle, while the excess mass flow rate is expanded in the HPV which controls the system high-pressure. Figure 2c presents the ejector and auxiliary evaporator (EJ,AUX) configuration, where an auxiliary evaporator is engaged between the ejector-HPV and the liquid receiver, providing cooling effect in the same chilled space where the main evaporator operates. The auxiliary evaporator helps extending the range of conditions in which the ejector can be used towards low ambient temperatures. A more detailed discussion on the role and the effects on the auxiliary evaporator can be found in Artuso et al. (2020).

The components included in this layout, selected according to market availability, and their main characteristics and weight are reported in Table 1.

Figure 2: MO unit: (a) back-pressure (BP) configuration; (b) ejector (EJ) configuration; (c) ejector and auxiliary evaporator (EJ,AUX) configuration. (Red: high pressure; green: low pressure; light-green: intermediate pressure; dashed lines: portions not used).

Table 1. List of components used in MO unit and their main characteristics

Component	Main characteristic	Weight
Compressor	Displacement: 21.6 cm ³ ; Speed: 1450 rev min ⁻¹	77.3 kg
Gas cooler	External heat exchange area: 16.9 m ²	18.0 kg
Evaporator	External heat exchange area: 19.7 m ²	35.4 kg
Auxiliary evaporator	External heat exchange area: 15.9 m ²	28.2 kg
Liquid separator	Internal volume: 10 L	5.0 kg

2.2 Fixed orifice unit

As a simpler and less complex alternative to the MO unit layout, a fixed orifice (FO) unit layout is proposed in this study, and its schematic is presented in Figure 3. The high-pressure is controlled through a variable-speed scroll compressor (operating between 1200 and 6000 rev min⁻¹), while the electronic high-pressure valve (HPV) is replaced by a fixed expansion valve (FEV).

Even for this layout, different configurations can occur. Figure 4a illustrates the fixed expansion valve (FEV) configuration while Figure 4b presents the ejector (EJ) configuration, where the two-phase ejector is used as the only expansion device. The meaning of the colours and of the dashed lines used in Fig. 4 is the same as in Fig. 2. Being the main goal of the FO unit layout the reduction of the system complexity compared to the MO unit layout, the auxiliary evaporator is not included in this layout. Further discussion on the exclusion of the auxiliary evaporator in the FO unit will be provided in the results section.

The components included in this layout, selected according to market availability, and their main characteristics and weight are reported in Table 2.

Figure 3: Fixed orifice (FO) unit layout

Figure 4: FO unit: (a) fixed expansion valve (FEV) configuration; (b) ejector (EJ) configuration. (Red: high pressure; green: low pressure; light-green: intermediate pressure; dashed lines: portions not used).

Table 2. List of components used in FO unit and their main characteristics

Component	Main characteristic	Weight
Compressor	Displacement: 6.7 cm ³ ; Speed: 25-100 rev s ⁻¹	13.8 kg
Gas cooler	External heat exchange area: 16.9 m ²	18.0 kg
Evaporator	External heat exchange area: 19.7 m ²	35.4 kg
Liquid separator	Internal volume: 10 L	5.0 kg

3. NUMERICAL EVALUATION

3.1 Cooling unit modelling approach

The numerical approach employed to simulate the cooling unit steady-state and dynamic performance is extensively described in previous studies by the same authors (Artuso et al., 2020; Fabris et al., 2021; Fabris et al., 2024b). For the sake of brevity, the main characteristics of the modelling approach are here reported, while a thorough description of the numerical model of each system component, including the formulation of differential equations and of the empirical correlations used to define the heat transfer coefficients can be found in the above-mentioned studies.

The numerical models are developed using the multi-physics commercial software Simcenter Amesim (Siemens, 2024). The numerical approach is based on discretizing real components into lumped parameter elements, mutually connected to represent the entire system. Each element is defined by nonlinear time-dependent differential equations, which are coupled in a system and integrated over time to solve the system dynamic behaviour.

The compressor performance is modelled through the calculation of volumetric and overall compression efficiency according to the compressor performance data (mass flow rate and power input) declared by the compressor manufacturer. The performance is provided in the form of third-order polynomial equations, as a function of suction and discharge pressures, based on ten coefficients declared by the compressor manufacturer and defined according to the EN12900 standard.

Heat exchangers are modelled discretizing the total heat exchange surface into a series of longitudinal lumped volumes, in a perfect counter-flow configuration. This modelling approach has been validated comparing the computed cooling effect against nominal data of heat exchangers reported in technical datasheets (Fabris et al., 2021). For each lumped volume, three elements representing the internal refrigerant flow, the pipe and fins material, and the external air flow, respectively, are considered. Differential equations accounting for internal convection, conduction through the pipe walls and fins and external convection are used. To accurately reproduce the sharp property change in supercritical conditions, a higher number of lumped volumes (18) is used for the gas cooler than for the evaporator

(6 volumes).

The ejector model is based on the performance data of an ejector specifically designed for MT transport refrigeration application (Fabris et al., 2024b). The performance maps of the ejector in different operating conditions are implemented into the cooling unit model: for each time step, the boundary conditions at the ejector ports are used to determine the performance of the ejector (motive mass flow rate, entrainment ratio) through linear interpolation of the ejector performance maps.

The high-pressure control is performed by a Proportional-Integral (PI) controller as a function of the gas cooler outlet temperature, to set it to the optimal heat rejection pressure as defined by Liao et al. (2000) in transcritical operation, while to a saturation pressure leading to a temperature approach equal to 3 K at the gas cooler outlet in subcritical operation. In the MO unit layout, the PI controls the opening of the HPV valve, while in the FO unit layout it controls the compressor speed.

3.2 Carbon footprint evaluation

A quasi-steady-state numerical approach is used to evaluate the equivalent CO₂ emissions associated with the TRU operation when employed on a refrigerated van in a short-range multi-drop delivery mission in urban environment. The programming environment used to estimate energy consumption and emissions is MATLAB (Mathworks, 2024).

Four different climatic conditions (EnergyPlus, 2025) are considered with one hour time step for the carbon footprint evaluation: Helsinki (humid continental, warm summer – Dfb under the Köppen-Geiger system; Kottek, 2006), Strasbourg (temperate oceanic climate - Cfb), Athens (hot-summer Mediterranean climate - Csa) and Phoenix (hot desert climate - BWh).

3.2.1 Average delivery mission

The short-range delivery mission is defined setting a daily travelled distance equal to 150 km, with an average vehicle velocity equal to 18.9 km h⁻¹ (based on the WLTP Class 3a Urban Cycle definition). Over the delivery mission time, 20 stops with the duration of 5 minutes each are considered, in which the box doors are open and external air infiltration occurs. A 1-hour additional stop is considered to account that drivers have the obligation to stop at least for one hour after four consecutive hours of driving. The resulting mission duration is equal to 10.6 hours. To account for the thermal loads variability over the day, it has been considered that the delivery mission can occur between 08:00 and 22:00. The thermal loads are therefore calculated for each hour within this span, but then proportionally reduced to account for the actual mission duration (10.6 hours) within the considered 14-hours span.

The insulated box external dimensions are 3.1m×2.2m×2.1m, representative of a light commercial vehicle. The operating internal air temperature set-point is 0°C, for fresh products preservation. The insulated box global heat transfer coefficient K is 0.60 W m⁻² K⁻¹.

Given the numerical model inputs (ambient conditions and mission definition), the main thermal loads in the insulated box are computed. The pulldown load corresponds to the energy required to lower the box temperature from an initial stationary temperature to the operational set-point and it is estimated based on the experimental characterization reported by Artuso et al. (2019). The stationary equilibrium temperature was assumed to be the mean value between the average ambient temperature for the given day and location and the internal air set-point (0°C). The conduction-convection heat infiltration is modelled according to the global heat transfer coefficient (K), as defined in the ATP agreement (United Nations, 2024). The sensible and latent infiltration load is evaluated based on the conservative assumption that, during each of the 5-minute door openings, the entire air volume inside the insulated box is replaced by external air (characterized by temperature and relative humidity of the ambient), which needs to be pulled down to the temperature set-point. It has to be pointed out that previous studies demonstrated that radiation load is significant for refrigerated vehicles only if long stops are considered (Artuso et al., 2019). In fact, when the truck is in motion, the external convection between outer surface of the insulated body and the ambient air is sufficient to maintain the surface temperature close to the ambient level. In this study, it is assumed that pulldown operations take place in the warehouse where the food products to be delivered are stored, with the vehicle kept in shade and not

exposed to direct solar radiation. For these reasons, solar radiation is not included in the model.

Given the hourly ambient temperatures, the TRU performance (cooling effect and COP) is calculated through the numerical evaluation described in Section 3.1. However, a COP degradation factor is applied following the EN 14825 approach to account for partialisation, as the hourly thermal load might result lower than the nominal cooling effect of the unit in those operating conditions.

From the values of thermal loads and COP, the power consumption of the unit for each hour of the year can be calculated. This value is then averaged over the year and, considering the mission duration, it leads to the yearly average mission energy consumption.

The TRU is assumed to be powered by the vehicle main engine through a belt connection to the driveline. Accordingly, a carbon conversion factor equal to $651 \text{ g}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}} \text{ kWh}^{-1}$ (Grigoratos et al., 2019) has been used. The CO_2 emissions linked to the extra fuel consumption needed to transport the weight of the TRU is also considered with a conversion factor equal to $37.5 \text{ g}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}} \text{ ton}^{-1} \text{ km}^{-1}$ (Fabris et al., 2024a).

3.2.2 Life cycle evaluation

A simplified assessment of the carbon footprint of the considered TRUs over their life cycle is conducted based on the structure described in Fabris et al. (2024a).

The average age of light commercial vehicles in use in Europe, equal to 12.0 years (ACEA, 2023), is assumed as the TRU lifetime. The yearly operation is assumed to be characterized by repetitions of the average delivery mission, calculated as described in Section 3.2.1, for 250 days in the year (Li, 2017).

Being the total refrigerant charge of unit 4.5 kg of R744, direct leakage emissions are calculated assuming a yearly leakage rate of 15% (Tassou et al., 2009; Li, 2017; Wu et al., 2022) and assuming that, during the TRU dismantling at end of life, the whole R744 charge is released in the atmosphere, given its low GWP (equal to 1), almost negligible compared to traditionally used refrigerants such as R404A ($\text{GWP}_{100} = 3922$) and R134a ($\text{GWP}_{100} = 1530$) or to retrofitting fluids used in latest years such as R452A ($\text{GWP}_{100} = 2141$), and its harmfulness towards environment.

CO_2 refrigerant is primarily recovered from industrial processes via Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS). The average carbon footprint associated with the CCS process, accounting for various technological pathways, is estimated at approximately $0.14 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}$ per kg of CO_2 captured (Rubin et al., 2015). Additional compression and purification steps are required to achieve purity and avoid excessive H_2O and non-condensable gases, and the associated carbon footprint is estimated in $0.04 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}$ per kg of CO_2 processed (Posch and Haider, 2012).

Electrical energy consumption factors equal to 4.22 kWh/kg and to 2.69 kWh/kg are assumed for the TRUs manufacturing and recycling processes, respectively (Wu et al., 2022). The carbon footprint linked to these processes is then evaluated considering the average GHG emission intensity of the electricity generation in Europe, equal to $0.21 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{kWh}$ (EEA, 2025).

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

4.1 Cooling unit performance

Firstly, the numerically evaluated steady-state performance of the different cooling unit layouts and configurations is presented under different ambient temperature conditions.

4.1.1 Modulated orifice unit

The steady-state performance of the MO unit, in each of its possible configurations, is presented in Figure 5. Figure 5a and 5b present the cooling unit thermodynamic COP and overall COP, respectively, defined as:

$$\text{COP}_{th} = \frac{Q_c}{P_{comp}} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

$$COP = \frac{Q_c - P_{fans,ev}}{P_{comp} + P_{fans,ev} + P_{fans,gc}} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

where Q_c represents the cooling effect provided by the refrigeration system, P_{comp} the compressor power input and P_{fans} the power consumption of fans, which for the evaporator represents an additional thermal load and power consumption at the same time. The cooling effect Q_c is presented in Figure 5c.

When using the ejector (EJ and EJ,AUX), only $T_{amb} > 20^\circ\text{C}$ is considered since, at lower ambient temperatures, the motive energy of the refrigerant flow at the outlet of the gas cooler (and, therefore, at the ejector motive nozzle) is too low to entrain mass flow rate at the ejector suction nozzle. Moreover, a fixed opening ratio of the expansion valve EV (Figure 1) is assumed, corresponding to the value resulting in the pressure lift maximizing COP at design conditions ($T_{amb} = 30^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure 5: MO unit steady-state performance for $T_i = 0^\circ\text{C}$ and different T_{amb} : (a) thermodynamic COP; (b) COP; (c) cooling effect

Figure 5a shows that the thermodynamic COP of the unit operating in ejector configurations is always significantly higher than in BP configuration. Moreover, the auxiliary evaporator is more beneficial towards lower ambient temperature conditions (for $T_{amb} = 20^\circ\text{C}$ the COP_{th} improvement between EJ,AUX and EJ configurations is equal to +5.7%), while at higher ambient temperatures the auxiliary evaporator becomes counterproductive (-2.1% in COP_{th} for $T_{amb} = 40^\circ\text{C}$), in agreement with the results presented in Artuso et al. (2020). However, when accounting for the additional thermal load and additional power consumption of the evaporator fans (Figure 5b), the EJ,AUX configuration (two evaporators, therefore two fans) presents a lower overall COP than the EJ configuration for almost every considered operating condition.

Moreover, considering the cooling effect (Figure 5c), the EJ,AUX configuration delivers the maximum cooling effect increase, compared to the BP configuration, for low ambient temperatures, when the actual cooling demand is lower. On the contrary, the EJ configuration presents the maximum increase in cooling capacity for high ambient temperatures, when it is needed the most due to higher thermal loads.

Following the numerical results described above, and at the same time considering the resolution of achieving a less complex cooling unit layout for the FO system compared to the MO system, the EJ,AUX configuration is not considered among the possible configurations in the FO unit layout.

4.1.2 Fixed orifice unit

The steady-state performance of the FO unit, in each of its possible configurations, is presented in Figure 6, in which the overall COP, as defined in Eq. (2), is reported in Figure 6a, while the cooling effect is reported in Figure 6b.

The EJ configuration leads to a significant increase of the overall COP compared to the FEV configuration, ranging from +15.4% at $T_{amb} = 20^{\circ}\text{C}$ to +28.6% at $T_{amb} = 40^{\circ}\text{C}$. Conversely, in FEV configuration, Q_c decreases with increasing T_{amb} , while the opposite occurs for the EJ configuration, thanks to the increased motive energy of the refrigerant flow exploited by the ejector, allowing for higher cooling capacity when high thermal loads occur. It is worth pointing out that the ejector cycle could allow installation of less oversized TRUs in refrigerated vehicles, since the mismatch between cooling demand and cooling capacity for high T_{amb} , requiring oversizing the unit compared to nominal operating conditions during the system design, is mitigated by the increased capacity achieved with EJ configuration in such peak load conditions.

Comparing Figures 5b and 6a, it can be observed that the COP of the FO unit is considerably higher than the COP of the MO unit: considering the EJ configuration for both layouts, the COP increase of the FO unit ranges from +22.2% for $T_{amb} = 20^{\circ}\text{C}$ to +6.2% for $T_{amb} = 40^{\circ}\text{C}$. The reason mainly lies in the superior isentropic efficiency of the variable-speed scroll compressor of the FO unit compared to the fixed-speed semi-hermetic compressor of the MO unit (up to +10% for lower ambient temperatures). In addition, in the MO unit in EJ configuration, a portion of the mass flow rate expands in the HPV and cannot be exploited by the ejector, resulting in an additional COP decrease compared to the FO unit in EJ configuration.

Figure 6: FO unit steady-state performance for $T_i = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and different T_{amb} : (a) COP; (b) cooling effect

4.1.3 Influence of pressure lift optimization

The results presented in Figures 5 and 6 are obtained for a fixed opening of the expansion valve EV. To evaluate the effect of the pressure lift optimization on the performance also for off-design operation, the optimal EV opening ratio (maximizing COP) is evaluated by solving $\frac{\partial \text{COP}}{\partial \Delta p_{lift}} = 0$ at each T_{amb} . Numerical results are presented in Figure 7 for FO unit in EJ configuration. The increase of the unit COP associated to the optimization of the ejector pressure lift is quite limited and reaches +3.8% at $T_{amb} = 20^{\circ}\text{C}$. On the other hand, the variation in cooling effect between optimized and non-optimized cases is almost null (under $\pm 0.3\%$).

Figure 7: Influence of the ejector pressure lift optimization on the cooling unit steady-state performance, for the FO unit in EJ configuration: (a) COP; (b) cooling effect

4.1.4 Influence of evaporator size

The evaporator size has a direct influence on the cooling unit performance, as larger evaporators can allow for higher evaporation pressures for a specific air temperature set-point leading, consequently, to higher COPs. To evaluate the influence of the evaporator size on the cooling unit performance employing the FO layout, a larger and a smaller evaporator are selected as an alternative to the reference evaporator reported in Table 2. The main characteristics of the reference and of the alternative evaporators are reported in Table 3, while the resulting performance of the FO cooling unit is presented in Figure 8.

Table 3. Different evaporators considered in FO unit and their main characteristics

Component	Main characteristic	Weight
Reference evaporator	External heat exchange area: 19.7 m ²	35.4 kg
Large evaporator	External heat exchange area: 29.5 m ²	49.3 kg
Small evaporator	External heat exchange area: 15.9 m ²	28.4 kg

Figure 8: Influence of the evaporator size on the cooling unit steady-state performance of the FO unit: (a) COP; (b) cooling effect

As expected, a larger evaporator than the reference one leads to an increase in COP for every ambient temperature condition: the COP increases between +6.1% and +3.3% in FEV configuration and between +0.7% and +3.4% in EJ configuration (for T_{amb} varying between 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). On the contrary, the smaller evaporator leads to a significant drop of the performance, with a COP decrease between -14.0% and -7.1% in FEV configuration and between -2.8% and -7.2% in EJ configuration (for T_{amb} varying between 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$).

The trend of the cooling effect in FEV configuration (Fig. 8b) is more complex than the one of the COP, as it is the result of the equilibrium conditions reached by the different systems, in terms of evaporation pressure and mass flow rate.

Given the ambient temperature, the gas cooler outlet condition converges to similar values for all the selected evaporators, thanks to the sizing of the gas cooler, which can properly work within the required range. As the high pressure is actively controlled as function of the gas cooler outlet condition, all the systems converge also to similar high pressures.

Conversely, the evaporation pressure and the mass flow rate have to change to satisfy both the heat balance at the evaporator (Eq. 3) and the pressure drop through the fixed expansion device (Eq. 4):

$$K S_{ev} \Delta T = \dot{m} \Delta h \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

$$\Delta p \sim k_{orifice} \dot{m} \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

In first approximation, neglecting minor dependencies such as, for example, the compressor efficiency changes as function of pressure ratio, the equilibrium is then governed by a system of two highly non-linear equations 3 and 4. According to the dynamic numerical results on this system, the equilibrium point for low ambient temperatures changes according to the following: a reduction of the evaporator exchange area decreases the equilibrium evaporation pressure/temperature; increases the pressure drop in the expansion device, that forces the compressor to provide a higher flow rate to sustain the design high-pressure; increases the cooling power (mostly related to the increase of the mass flow). This equilibrium is possible until the compressor reaches its maximum speed. After this point ($T_{amb} \sim$

25°C for the small evaporator and $T_{amb} \sim 38^\circ\text{C}$ for the standard one) the optimal high pressure cannot be realized, the compressor runs at full speed and the cycle capacity decreases with a higher slope.

The cooling capacity of the EJ, conversely, demonstrates a minimal sensitivity to the evaporator size, with the larger and smaller evaporator following the trend of the reference system with slightly smaller and higher cooling power, respectively. The higher regularity of this system comes from the presence of the ejector and the adopted control logic for the high pressure. In EJ system the high pressure depends only on the mass flow rate and the thermodynamic conditions at ejector motive nozzle. Due to the supersonic flow in the motive nozzle, the evaporation pressure does not exert any major feedback on the high-pressure side, avoiding the highly nonlinear system discussed in the FEV layout.

4.2 Influence of climatic conditions on carbon footprint

The carbon footprint of a transport refrigeration unit depends both on its primary energy consumption and on the additional fuel consumption required to carry the weight of the TRU. Therefore, a trade-off between system complexity, thermodynamic performance, components and weight needs to be considered to optimize the system, evaluating the carbon equivalent overall emissions. Data for each of the cooling unit layouts considered in this study and for different climatic conditions, obtained as an average of the yearly emissions on a single delivery mission, are reported in Table 4.

In yearly calculations, cooling unit operation is considered only for $T_{amb} > 10^\circ\text{C}$, and when multiple configurations are available the most performing for each ambient temperature was considered, thus EJ for $T_{amb} > 20^\circ\text{C}$ and baseline cycle for $10^\circ\text{C} < T_{amb} < 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 4. Average delivery mission $\text{CO}_{2,\text{eq}}$ emissions as a function of cooling unit layout and climatic conditions.

Cooling unit	$\text{CO}_{2,\text{eq}}$ due to energy consumption [kg]				$\text{CO}_{2,\text{eq}}$ due to TRU weight [kg]		Total $\text{CO}_{2,\text{eq}}$ [kg]			
	Hel	Str	Ath	Pho	Total	Δ from FO	Hel	Str	Ath	Pho
MO unit	1.02	1.79	3.45	4.89	0.95	(+0.52)	1.97	2.73	4.40	5.84
FO unit	0.86	1.50	2.94	4.36	0.43	(+0.00)	1.29	1.93	3.38	4.79
FO unit with large evap.	0.84	1.48	2.90	4.27	0.51	(+0.08)	1.35	1.99	3.41	4.78
FO unit with small evap.	0.95	1.62	3.15	4.65	0.39	(-0.04)	1.34	2.01	3.54	5.04

Carbon emissions due to the energy consumption are strongly influenced by the climatic conditions as the operation of the cooling unit directly depends on the thermal load, which is increasing for warmer climates. On the contrary, the emissions associated with the cooling unit weight depend only on the unit layout and components selection.

The MO unit is outperformed by the FO unit in every climatic condition. In fact, the FO unit presents the double advantage of a better thermodynamic performance and a lower weight, mostly thanks to the good performance and extremely low weight of the scroll compressor compared to the semi-hermetic compressor employed in the MO unit. In particular, the FO unit (with reference evaporator) presents a total emission reduction compared to the MO unit equal to -34.5% in cold climate (Helsinki) and to -18.0% in harsh climate (Phoenix).

Results also clearly highlight the crucial importance of a correct sizing of the heat exchangers in transport refrigeration applications. An undersized evaporator reduces the overall weight of the cooling unit, decreasing the emissions linked to TRU weight during vehicle motion. However, the significant deterioration of the thermodynamic performance increases the energy-related emissions, leading to a worse overall result when compared to the reference evaporator for all the considered climatic conditions (from +3.8% to +5.2% emissions). On the other hand, an oversized evaporator increases the unit COP, but the weight-related emissions compensate and overcome the effects of a higher COP in

almost all the considered climatic conditions, especially for colder climates, where the cooling unit operates for less hours in the year. In Helsinki, the increase of overall carbon footprint with larger evaporator is +4.4% compared to the reference evaporator case. In Phoenix, a slight decrease (-0.3%) of the overall carbon footprint is achieved, suggesting that an oversized evaporator might have a beneficial effect under extreme climatic conditions.

Finally, a simplified analysis of the carbon footprint of the entire TRU life cycle is conducted, to assess the influence of the unit manufacturing and decommissioning and of the refrigerant production and leakages on the overall results. Results are reported in Table 5.

The equivalent CO₂ emissions linked to the phases of production and end of life of the system have a marginal impact on the overall carbon footprint related to the entire life cycle (ranging from approximately 4% in cold climates to approximately 1% in hot climates). Equivalent emissions due to refrigerant leakages are almost negligible (less than 1% of the overall carbon footprint) thanks to the very low GWP of R744.

This sensitivity study allows to conclude that the optimum compromise between TRU complexity, performance and weight can be focused on the system operations as most of the system carbon footprint comes from primary energy consumption during operation and from the additional fuel consumption to carry the TRU weight. Considering the FO unit with reference evaporator, the weight-related emissions range between 32% (in cold climates) to 9% (in hot climates) of the overall life cycle carbon footprint.

Table 5. Carbon footprint of the cooling units over their entire life cycle.

		MO unit	FO unit (ref. evap.)	FO unit (large evap.)	FO unit (small evap.)
Operation [kg]	Hel	3063	2577	2845	2512
	Str	5354	4502	4858	4440
	Ath	10349	8834	9443	8706
	Pho	14673	13078	13945	12803
Weight [kg]		2842	1294	1529	1173
Leakages [kg]		13	13	13	13
Refrigerant production [kg]		2	2	2	2
Unit production [kg]		145	64	76	58
Unit end of life [kg]		93	41	49	37

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, different design solutions for a R744 cooling unit for road transport refrigeration of fresh products in urban environment (design cooling power 4-5 kW at 0°C) are analysed. The effects of different layouts, controls and components are numerically evaluated, firstly focusing on the thermodynamic performance of each solution, and then considering the trade-off between performance improvement and weight reduction, to reduce the overall carbon footprint of the transport refrigeration unit.

The inclusion of an ejector in the unit layout always leads to an increase of the COP between +7.3% to +19.5% for the modulated orifice unit and between +15.4% to +28.6% for the fixed orifice unit, with ambient temperature ranging from 20°C to 40°C. The fixed orifice unit layout with variable-speed compressor for high-pressure control outperforms the modulated orifice layout with fixed-speed semi-hermetic compressor and HPV control, showing a COP increase ranging from +22.2% to +6.2% with ambient temperature ranging from 20°C to 40°C, respectively.

On a yearly average delivery mission, the modulated orifice layout can achieve a reduction in carbon emissions between -17.9% and -34.4%, depending on climatic conditions. The scroll compressor used in the FO unit presents the double advantage of increasing the unit COP and at the same time reducing

the weight of the unit.

An undersized evaporator is always counterproductive, as it significantly decreases the unit COP, leading to an increase of the carbon footprint of the average delivery mission between +3.8% and +5.2%. On the other hand, even the use of an oversized evaporator might increase the mission carbon footprint up to +4.4%, as the COP improvement is overcome by the increased weight-related emissions, highlighting that such a solution might be beneficial only in extreme hot weather.

Over the entire life cycle of the transport cooling unit, more than 95% of the carbon footprint is related to primary energy consumption to power the unit and to fuel-related emissions to transport the unit weight, with the proportion between these two contributions being affected by the climatic conditions. The use of natural refrigerant R744 helps reducing to negligible values the direct emissions linked to leakages over the unit life cycle.

NOMENCLATURE

Acronyms

BP	Back-pressure configuration	FO	Fixed orifice unit layout
COP	Coefficient of performance	GWP	Global warming potential
EJ	Ejector configuration	HPV	High-pressure valve
EJ,AUX	Ejector and auxiliary evaporator configuration	MO	Modulated orifice unit layout
EV	Expansion valve	TRU	Transport refrigeration unit
FEV	Fixed expansion valve configuration		

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